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Deliverable D3.11

Lessons learned and policy recommendations relating to how European fleet international- and SFPA water fisheries could be managed and conducted

22/11/2021

Executive Summary

This report synthesises the main findings from the value chain- and governance analysis in FarFish, and point at some potential policy changes that could improve governance of the SFPAs and the high seas fisheries of the European external fishing fleet.

This is the final deliverable from work package 3 (WP3) of the FarFish project, containing lessons learned and policy recommendations based on the work conducted in *T3.1 Evaluation of governance structures* and *T3.2 Value chain analysis*. The overall objective of FarFish is to improve knowledge on and management of EU fisheries outside Europe, while contributing to sustainability and long-term profitability. To this end, WP3 has conducted value chain analysis and evaluations of the governance structure of the EU external fishing fleet in the selected case studies. The studies have provided insights to how these fisheries are managed and conducted, and how the fisheries are utilized and are contributing to the seafood supply, including to the European market and partner countries.

This report synthesises the main findings from these studies. Based on the lessons learned as well as interaction with other areas within the project, we discuss recommendations for potential policy changes that could improve governance of the SFPAs and European high seas fisheries. The fisheries and value chains analysed are highly professional and are based on the different companies' commercial considerations. The recommendations to improve the performance of these companies or to achieve wider socio-economic goals are therefore directed at the potential for changes and improvements by way of regulations. The suggestions would in most cases require further elaboration and discussions, hence the term potential.

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1 Introduction

This is the final deliverable from work package 3 (WP3) of the FarFish project, containing lessons learned and policy recommendations based on the work conducted in *T3.1 Evaluation of governance structures* and *T3.2 Value chain analysis*. The overall objective of FarFish is to improve knowledge on and management of EU fisheries outside Europe, while contributing to sustainability and long-term profitability. To this end, WP3 has conducted value chain analysis and evaluations of the governance structure of the EU external fishing fleet in the selected case studies. The studies have provided insights to how these fisheries are managed and conducted, and how the fisheries are utilized and are contributing to the seafood supply, including to the European market and partner countries.

In *Task 3.1* three deliverables are submitted:

D3.3 Report on evaluation of governance structures of the cases, containing a presentation of the governance structures of the EU long-distance fishing fleet in the six case studies of the FarFish project. The report outlines the legal framework for the agreements, main achievements and identified challenges.

- *D3.8 Report on the governance of European fisheries in international- and SFPAs waters* contains a manuscript analysing the governance of the EU fisheries taking place in the Southwest Atlantic high seas. Taking as a departure the lack of an adequate regional framework that sets of rules to effectively manage and control the fisheries taking place in this area, the study presents the main challenges and discusses how the governance of the high seas fisheries in the SW Atlantic can be strengthened.
- *D3.10 Review on how European fleet international- and SFPAs water fisheries are managed and conducted* contains a manuscript analysing the development in the bilateral access agreements with Capo Verde, Mauritania, Senegal, and the Seychelles in terms of monitoring, control and surveillance (MCS) of the fisheries and how the reforms of the CFP (in 1992, 2002 and 2013) and changes in the external dimension of the EU fisheries policy are enshrined in the access agreements.

In *Task 3.2* two deliverables are submitted:

- *D3.4 Report on description of value chains of the CS* provides a generalised mapping and description of the seafood value chains for the six case studies covered by FarFish. The national configuration of the value chains differs quite substantially and are described.

- *D3.9 Report on the value chain analysis for EU fisheries in international- and SFPA waters* contains different analyses of selected value chains within the FarFish case studies. Due to the large differences encountered between the various value chains, the report contains three manuscripts, which address different value chains separately. The first manuscript discusses traceability aspects of the tuna value chains of Cabo Verde and Seychelles. The second manuscript investigates recent major changes in the value chain for small pelagics in Mauritania due to management changes in Mauritania, and discusses the impact of this to both the EU, Mauritania and West African region. The third manuscript investigates the Argentine hake fishery in the Southwest Atlantic, and discusses the supply of hake to the Spanish market, the potential implications of a supply shortfall due to reduced catches following sustainability advice, and the need to strive for certification. There is also a section discussing the West-African tuna SFPAs in unison.

This report synthesises the main findings from these studies. Based on the lessons learned as well as interaction with other areas within the project, we discuss recommendations for potential policy changes that could improve governance of the SFPAs and European high seas fisheries. The fisheries and value chains analysed are highly professional and are based on the different companies' commercial considerations. The recommendations to improve the performance of these companies or to achieve wider socio-economic goals are therefore directed at the potential for changes and improvements by way of regulations. The suggestions would in most cases require further elaboration and discussions, hence the term potential. We cannot claim to have achieved full understanding of the host countries' and EU' aims, causal links between these and the activities involved and trade-offs between aims.

2 The governance of SFPAs

The European Union has had bilateral fisheries agreements with countries in Africa and the Pacific for more than 40 years. Currently, there are 13 agreements in force, 9 tuna agreements and 4 mixed agreements. The FarFish project has analysed the governance of four of these agreements - Cabo Verde, Mauritania, Senegal and the Seychelles.

The bilateral access agreements have i.e. been heavily criticized for not being sustainable, for the lack of equity and limited economic benefit for the partner countries, and for lack of transparency. The EUs own evaluations have also generally concluded that the control of its external fishing fleet have been too weak (as is the control of other fleets operating in many of these waters). However, through the regular reforms of the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP) the EU has over time addressed many of the problems and criticisms raised related to the external policy of EU fisheries in non-European waters. New standards and management principles are introduced, and EU regulations to improve the governance of the external fleet are adopted, amended and repealed to be in line with current management principles and new technologies. In the FarFish project we analysed how the EU has been able to implement this policy in the bilateral fisheries access agreements, particularly related to monitoring, control and surveillance (MCS). This was done through a document analysis of the development of the four access agreements from the early agreements in the 1990ies until today. The access agreements provide fishing opportunities for a specified time period, usually four years after which they have to be prolonged or renegotiated. The development was analysed along three main areas: changes in the provisions on authorization of fishing vessels, new procedures and technologies for improved MCS, and new modes of cooperation between the parties.

The study shows that the provisions generally follow the development in the CFP and accompanying implementing regulations. For each renegotiation, new requirements for MCS have been introduced. In some cases, the requirements in the access agreements precede the enshrinement in EU regulations. Not surprisingly, a major change occurs with the introduction of FPA in 2002. Both the form, content, and level of detail in the Agreements and Protocols negotiated after this change clearly reflects new governing ideas and a commitment to better monitor this fleet.

Despite the strengthening of MCS requirements the implementation is often slow or even lacking. In some cases, it has taken several protocols from a requirement is first introduced before it is implemented. The observers requirement is an example where there over time has been implementation challenges. Observers was required already in the first access agreements with all the four countries. All EU vessels are obliged to take on board observers designated by the partner country through their observer programmes. Around 2005 the requirements in all the access agreements became more detailed, with descriptions of observer duties, embarkation, and reporting routines.

However, in all the cases there has been a persistent challenge of low observer coverage and a lack of trained observers. The requirement for observer coverage in the access agreements has however stayed unchanged (in three of the four cases), and without the partners, so far, being able to address the underlying challenge of ensuring the required number of observers. We rather observe that new Protocols provide admittedly more detailed provisions for embarkation conditions, and observers' duties and obligations. One might question this approach of setting and maintaining high standards without allocating sufficient resources, both by the EU and partner country, to ensure the requirements are met. The exception is in the Mauritanian agreement, where the requirement in 2012 was eased, from requiring observers on all vessels to only requiring observers on board two vessels per fishing category per year. In light of ensuring compliance with the requirements of the SFPAs, and also to not undermine their credibility, this, in combination with increased capacity building efforts stands out as a viable approach to the observer challenge.

The implementation of a regional observer's network to improve the monitoring of the industrial fleet operating in western Africa might also contribute to increased observer coverage in this region. Another approach is to introduce more technology and hence reduce the reliance on human observations. In Seychelles a decline in the observation coverage of the EU purse seine vessel operations is explained by the progressive introduction by EU operators of CCTV¹ observation systems. In addition, a pilot electronic observer scheme has been developed and was introduced in the latest Protocol. However, the effectiveness of these electronic system will depend on the capacity of the relevant authorities to receive and analyse these data. Resources must be allocated to educate analysts and to the actual analysis and to the processing and potential follow up of infringements in the SFPA-countries.

In the 2009 Control Regulation the term control observer was introduced, referring to a person authorized by a national authority to monitor the fishing vessel's compliance with the rules of the CFP. A Union control observer scheme was to be established for fisheries taking place within Community waters. In the proposal for amending the Control Regulation it is suggested to make these rules applicable also in the waters of third countries in which a Union vessel is operating.² In the four access agreements the observers' duties are mainly for scientific purposes. It is only in the Mauritanian Protocol it is explicitly stated that the observers shall ensure that the Union vessels operating in the Mauritanian fishing zone comply with the terms of the Protocol. If an EU control observer scheme are to be implemented in the SFPA fisheries, this might pose an opportunity to reconsider the existing observer programs.

¹ Closed-Circuit Television: a sset of cameras record all activities taking place on the deck and below. Video fottages are analysed by independent third parties.

² https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/A-9-2021-0016_EN.html

Physical inspection was not addressed in any of the access agreements until 2020, when it was introduced in the Seychelles SFPAs. It was termed “cooperation in the area of MCS and the fight against IUU fishing”. Here it is stated that the parties may agree to cooperate on and carry out joint inspection programs on Union vessels to ensure compliance with both Union and Seychelles legislation. In the other access agreements, cooperation on inspections is limited to authorizing representatives from the EU to participate as an observer. In the Mauritanian agreement there is a mutual system for shore-based controls. Here both parties shall designate representatives who shall attend monitoring operations and inspections with the aim of observing the implementation of the Protocol. This system was introduced already in 2006 and was extended to include controls both on land and at sea in 2015. The experiences from both the Seychelles and Mauritanian arrangement might pose good examples for other SFPAs.

The EU-IUU regulation requires inspection to be carried out on at least 5% of all landings and transshipments by third-country vessels in the ports of EU member states each year, and always if a vessel has been sighted conducting IUU fishing or is presumed to have done so.³ There are no minimum requirements for the number of inspections to be carried out, neither in port or at sea, in the access agreements analysed. This might be worth considering.

In line with the technological development in controlling fisheries, the use of electronic monitoring and reporting tools has also been introduced in the access agreements, but there are clear implementation challenges. Both the introduction of VMS and electronic reporting serve as examples of slow implementation and challenges of introducing new technology into the monitoring and control of these fisheries. Even though electronic reporting was to be implemented by EU vessels already in 2011, introducing ERS into the access agreements has been slow. In the Mauritanian agreement, with a protocol from 2015, ERS is not even mentioned. In the other agreements ERS was introduced in the 2014 Protocols, but as statements of intent to introduce ERS, and without any guidelines on how to implement it. In the latest Protocols negotiated in 2019 and 2020, ERS is included as a requirement, and guidelines for implementation and transition are attached. However, the wording clearly illustrates the challenges of implementing it, where the parties are committed to “define common arrangements to ensure that the transition to ERS takes place as soon as possible”. In general, there is a lack of resources within the area of MCS and it is likely to believe that the implementation of both VMS and ERS suffers from this as implementing electronic tools is resource demanding. When implemented, these ways of tracking and reporting fisheries activities should be less resource demanding than other ways of controlling fisheries, but this depends on the ability to replace existing

³ Council Regulation (EC) No 1005/2008 of 29 September 2008 establishing a Community system to prevent, deter and eliminate illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing, amending Regulations (EEC) No 2847/93, (EC) No 1936/2001 and (EC) No 601/2004 and repealing Regulations (EC) No 1093/94 and (EC) No 1447/1999

platforms. If they are not able to replace physical inspections or other controlling activities, this will rather be yet another platform in the struggle of scarce resources.

The gradual and slow implementation of MCS requirements observed in the study of the access agreements might be a viable approach and way for the EU to be able to implement its external fisheries policy and improve the control of the SFPAs fisheries, in particular when accompanied with capacity building initiatives and increased cooperation. Something we expect with the ERS. On the other hand, if the MCS requirements are not implemented, and are not adjusted to the actual situation, they may end up as paper-regulations which over time will undermine the credibility of the SFPAs.

The knowledge about the SFPAs fisheries are generally low and increased transparency could contribute to the understanding of how these fisheries are governed. For instance, there is little available information about the work of the joint scientific committees (JSCs) and the planning for and use of sectoral support. Availability of information on efforts to improve MCS and the improvements taking place could be improved. There is also limited knowledge about the socio-economic effects of SFPAs, for the partner countries and also the EU. Reporting of socio-economic data could be valuable for understanding the importance of these agreements.

3 The tuna SFPA value chains

Main findings and lessons learned

The tuna fisheries are among the world's most important fisheries and the products are traded in an integrated global market. There is extensive trade in especially raw materials, but also in intermediate products and finished goods. Transport of tuna from the main catching areas to processing sites is done through a fleet of reefers and to an increasing extent by containerized transport. EU is both a large importer of all these products as well as the main consumer market and with a large processing industry. Prices for raw materials are strongly influenced by the market in Thailand.

SFPA tuna contributes to this supply chain. The licensed fishing vessels utilize resources both within the case study EEZs, other countries' EEZ and the high seas, often combining these within the same trip, as they follow stock migrations. Economics likely has a strong influence on the harvesting pattern. The SFPAs are important for the EU fleet as they allow the vessels access to good tuna fishing areas and thus contributes positively to vessel profitability. This as it provides an opportunity to harvest where the perceived economic benefit is highest. In some cases, and periods this is within SFPAs. Fishing here also generally reduces steaming time from fishing grounds to port.

Offloading of catches varies, but the data made available by DG Mare show an increase in the case study countries Cabo Verde and Senegal. These countries have relatively large operating processing plants. Mauritania does not receive noteworthy landings of tuna, and has no major processing firms. The change in landing pattern is likely also linked to the discontinuation of the important SFPA with Gabon during the study period. The extensive trade means that offloading does not equate supply to local processing. Catches are commonly sold by traders before the fishing vessel docks. Some may be sold to local processors, while some is transhipped to other ports and processors. For both Cabo Verde and the Seychelles, data was available showing that the majority of offloaded tuna from EU vessels was transported away. For Senegal, qualitative information indicates that EU catches only to a little extent supplies local processing. Catches are sorted by dockside according to species and size categories, allowing processors to specialize and take advantage of competitive advantages and processing strategies. This supports a relatively large processing sector in EU, especially in Spain. Brands in southern Europe focus more strongly on the more expensive yellowfin and canned products in oil, while markets in the north are consuming more of the cheaper skipjack in brine.

Although a large share is transhipped away from Cabo Verde, Senegal and the Seychelles, the tuna supplies still support relatively large processors and provide significant job opportunities within these countries. Cabo Verde has two relatively large firms receiving about 37,000 tonnes of raw materials and employing about 2,200 persons. These process and distribute frozen whole, tuna loins and canned products. A very large share is exported to EU, primarily Spain. The firms here are to an extent vertically

and horizontally integrated with fishing vessels and processors in Europe. The extent SFPAs contribute to this activity is uncertain and difficult to assess. As EU vessels are the main supplier to Cabo Verde by far, it seems clear that the SFPAs are important in this regard. Without the opportunity to fish within the EEZ, EU vessels would find the area less attractive and would likely redistribute their fishing effort to areas where other ports provide better options. Partly this could be offset by better availability for local fleets, but these already face difficulties as their fishing opportunities are more restricted than the EU fleet. EU vessels employ local fishers, but compared to the processing activity this contribution is small.

In Senegal, the tuna from EU vessels is to a large extent transported to Abidjan for processing, which is the major purse seining port in the region and home to an extensive canning industry. The processing in Dakar is primarily supplied by local vessels as well as a Korean-controlled fleet. Thus, the SFPAs contribution to activity in Senegal is limited, and primarily linked to handling fish for transport. A positive contribution in this regard has been that Dakar is the hub for the EU pole-and-line fleet. This employs a large component of Senegalese sailors and is more labour intensive than purse seining. It also provides upstream ripple effects as they are supplied live bait by Senegalese artisanal fishers. Mauritanian SFPAs tuna is not offloaded locally, and is thus not supporting any activity or employment here.

With tuna primarily being processed and exported, the contribution to local food supply is relatively limited. However, some undersize and minor tuna species are sold on local markets and for restaurants catering for the tourist industry in Cabo Verde. In transshipment hubs such as Abidjan and Tema, receiving a large share of FAD purse seine catches as well as transshipment from other ports, these supplies support a relatively large activity and is more important in terms of local food supply and employment.

There has been a noteworthy shift in the tuna resource base that has implications for both vessel activities and profitability as well as for downstream processing industry. The composition of catches has shifted with the share of yellowfin being reduced and replaced by skipjack. With the former generally receiving prices that are about twice as high, this clearly has a strong negative impact on profits. In addition to this detrimental effect, the average size in catches has been reduced. Although we have been unable to obtain size differentiated price data, qualitative information indicates that this also has important negative impact. Data from ICCAT indicate that CPUE so far has been stable.

These effects have impacted both of the primary tuna vessel groups. In addition, particular challenges have been facing the pole-and-line vessels. Senegalese authorities have recently introduced restrictions on acquiring live bait with strong impacts. Some vessels have gone to sea without bait. Data show that they have expanded their fishing area, increasing costs. Coupled with price decrease,

the reduced profitability from these impacts has resulted in some vessels leaving the area and others being moored.

The SFPA host countries enjoy preferential tariffs when exporting to the EU. EU rules of origin provides tariff-free trade for locally or EU-caught tuna that is processed in the host country. With other suppliers of tuna products generally being more productive, the tariffs have an important role in maintaining local processing competitive. This also places EU vessels in a strong negotiating position compared to other fleets. Cabo Verde has been granted tariff-free quotas for non-originating products for some years. The importance of tariffs was highlighted when prolonging these quotas were delayed in 2021, leading to the processor announcing lay-offs of employees and reduced activity.

EU vessels are required to provide a considerable amount of data for monitoring and surveillance purposes to combat IUU fishing. Some of these data are relayed to the host country, allowing for cross-checks and validation. A large share of the EU fleet has also implemented innovative camera-based monitoring systems, with third-party companies investigating these data. In contrast, there are concerns that other fleets are not providing sufficient information about tuna catches.

Processors of tuna are operating systems that allow for tuna products to be traced from retail to fishing vessel and catching area. Their primary purpose has been food security, but traceability can also bring benefits concerning IUU fishing. EU vessels record detailed information about catches and are to some extent able to maintain this by separating catches in wells aboard. There are, however, both opportunities and economic incentives to misreport. Especially related to catches inside SPFA that are met with a per tonne fee, but also to misreporting of yellowfin as quotas have been introduced. EU has also implemented a catch certificate system for imports to the EU. Especially as there is no central electronic registry of catch certificates, there are opportunities to bypass this system.

Potential policy recommendations

As the tuna value chains are globally integrated and mature, clear improvements to the value chain organisation are difficult to identify. The main areas for improvement that can be influenced by policy are likely found in the management of the fisheries and ensuring that resources are sustainably harvested. As some stocks are currently overfished, reduced fishing effort and catches can potentially improve yield and reduce harvesting costs. This could also allow for higher average fish sizes providing higher value and less processing cost. Informants have also stated that there is considerable underreporting of catches within IOTC. This can be achieved through continued efforts in the relevant RFMOs. Some informants called for better cooperation between the EU and coastal states within the RFMOs to avoid having only one party advocating for improvements.

EU vessels are at the forefront in monitoring and control systems. These systems can be further improved using technology and better systems for monitoring. The potential from camera-based systems can be evaluated and considered for mandatory implementation. While EU vessels are advanced in reporting, other fleets are providing little data and their activities are difficult to monitor and control. For example, Senegalese authorities in charge of monitoring landings in Dakar complained about the lack of collaboration from certain companies under Asian capital. Therefore, these authorities often focus their work on more collaborative companies. In negotiations with host countries concerning SFPAs, the EU can advocate for improved standards in reporting from especially these other fleets, including local industrial and artisanal vessels, to allow for better management.

SFPA host countries have mentioned that there are technical issues in the transfer of data from EU vessels and that there are discrepancies between different streams of data provided to the RFMOs. Having access to better data from EU vessels can ease the host country activities in ensuring compliance with protocol requirements and fishing fee payments. This can also contribute to the perception of equitable distribution of benefits from resources. These can be amended through for example the grants from the agreement. As such an example of good practice, Côte d'Ivoire has created a dedicated marine surveillance office, which collects electronic data from vessels active in its waters. This modern infrastructure was funded by the EU under the SFPA, and appears to increase the country's surveillance capacities.

In the Seychelles, bringing bycatch to shore is mandatory. This could be implemented for the other tuna SFPAs as well and would contribute to local supply of raw materials. Although not major quantities, these raw materials are less likely to be transhipped and of less value. They would therefore to a larger extent be processed locally and facilitate job opportunities. With less value, they are also more likely to enter local markets and increase food supply and local ripple effects from downstream activities.

Another point was the redundancies in the local seamen boarding constraints in each country. These constraints require additional crew rotation, which is a waste of time and requires forced journeys to the ports. In addition, the recent context of covid-19 has further complicated these crew rotations. In this case, some shipowners recommended setting up a regional crew agency led by West African countries, which would organize and centralize the distribution of West African seamen to foreign vessels.

The processing industry in Cabo Verde and the Seychelles seems fairly dependent on the current tariff regime to remain competitive against countries with less processing costs. Especially the tariff free quotas for non-originating products caused recent problems and announced processing lay-offs in Cabo Verde. Providing the host countries a longer-term security about the tariff situation could allow

processors to make better decisions concerning capacity and how to source raw materials. In case of favourable tariff regimes being secured, this could lead to increased local processing. With this in mind, Côte d'Ivoire has for example created a free zone for companies located in the port of Abidjan, including tax exemptions. This allows national companies to be competitive against competing industries in Ghana or Dakar. In this case, the competitiveness issues take place at a country-level.

Although the tonnage fee currently is relatively low, having these fixed over relatively long durations increases risk for vessel owners and could contribute to fishing being unprofitable. An option to reduce this could be to link these payments to market prices for tuna. Uniform fees across species as currently practiced also theoretically gives incentives to target the higher valued species such as yellowfin. This could contribute towards higher fishing pressure on stocks that are overexploited. Differentiating fees between species could reduce such incentives, but of course strengthens incentives to misreport species composition.

The EU could also promote equal standards to be employed for all flags utilizing tuna resources within the SFPAs. This could apply to vessel monitoring and reporting as well as licensing and tonnage fees. This could contribute to a more level playing field between fishing actors and promote sustainability.

4 The small pelagics chain in Mauritania

Main findings and lessons learned

The small pelagics fished under the Mauritanian SFPAs is the largest fishery and the SFPAs are the biggest in terms of value. Mauritania had to a large extent relied on vessels from the former eastern bloc countries in the exploitation of the rich pelagic resources. After the collapse of the Soviet Union, this activity was strongly reduced. Dutch factory trawler vessels were invited and started fishing in 1995 and included in an agreement with the EU from 1996. These EU vessels have been fishing for primarily sardinella and horse mackerel and were joined by trawlers from eastern Europe, and being included in the EU agreement after joining the EU. Catches were frozen on board and sardinella sold to Gulf of Guinea countries for human consumption, while mackerel was primarily sold to markets in Eastern Europe. Catches were also primarily landed in Las Palmas, thus not contributing to local activity or employment apart from Mauritanian sailors employed on the vessels.

With the agreement covering 2012-2014, there was a strong shift in management from the Mauritanian authorities, having a strong impact on the EU small pelagic fisheries. To improve local benefits and ripple effects from their rich resources, EU vessels were limited to fishing outside of 20 nautical miles from shore. Vessels were also required to land in Mauritania. The fishing area restriction meant that the foreign trawlers lost access to the primary fishing grounds for sardinella. The infrastructure in Nouadhibou was also not sufficient to accommodate some of the large trawlers.

This led to catches being strongly reduced, from about 300,000 tonnes to now about one third. The EU fleet is now primarily fishing horse and jack mackerel and sardine. These are frozen at sea and respectively supplied to primarily Russia and canning factories in Brazil and South Africa. A large quantity frozen fish is also exported to Gulf of Guinea countries (Nigeria, Benin, Cote d'Ivoire, etc.). The profitability of these fisheries has been reduced, seeing not only a reduction in the sardinella fleet but also the other trawlers. Vessels participating in these fisheries have been reduced from 18 in 2014 to 7 in 2019. Infrastructure in Mauritania has been considerably improved, so vessels have little problems landing there, and the offloading, storage and container transfer contributes to local activity and employment, although modest.

Mauritanian authorities also introduced another measure to strengthen the local impact and to promote food security and fish consumption in areas from the coast. Foreign vessels were obliged to donate 2% of their catches to Mauritania. This fish has been distributed by SINDP, a state-run agency, to remote areas, also developing cold chains and establishing distribution hubs. Fish are sold at reduced prices and thus contributes to food security.

The fleet catching sardinella has been replaced first with Senegalese canoe purse seiners and later with modern coastal purse seiners, many from Turkey. On shore in Mauritania a large fish meal and oil

processing industry has been developed and grown from 2 to 40 plants from 2010 to 2020. The purse seiners supply this industry with large quantities of fresh pelagics and production of fishmeal was about 125,000 tonnes in 2020, corresponding to about 600,000 tonnes of pelagics.

An EU-owned processing plant is operating in Mauritania, but has been operating at low capacity utilization having problems acquiring quality raw materials, among other factors. This change in the value chain has of course shifted production from being a relatively cheap supply of nutrient rich food for sub-Saharan countries to aquaculture, livestock and other demanding fish meal and oil.

Potential policy recommendations

Contrary to the tuna cases, being quite mature value chains, the small pelagics in Mauritania is much younger, operating in a difficult business environment and with larger constraints being imposed on it. This hinders the market in finding the most efficient organisation and product mix and suggests that there are more opportunities to be found that could increase value adding. Though, also in this case the highest benefits are likely achieved through improved fisheries management. The sardinella and bonga shad stocks are likely overexploited. Improved management could contribute to higher long run yield and reduced risk of stock collapse. Hence both EU and Mauritanian authorities should promote sustainable harvesting and contribute to ensuring a sustainable fishing effort being applied in the fisheries. Developing improved knowledge about ecosystem dynamics should be part of such efforts. Both economic theory and practical experience has given insight into how poorly regulated fisheries waste value and creates problems for downstream utilization. Thus, improving the regulation of the fishing fleet could contribute to realizing benefits for the whole value chain. The EU also has considerable experience in developing vessel licensing and capacity reduction programmes that could be beneficial to Mauritanian efforts in this regard. The EU could also contribute towards developing better monitoring and control systems that would play a strong role if fishing effort is to be reduced.

Of course, in many cases there are other policy goals to fisheries than simply optimizing value adding. As we have seen in the Mauritania case, the authorities wished to increase local ripple effects and especially employment from the utilization of their resources. Making the trade-off between potential revenues and other positive impacts is a difficult exercise that needs to be made locally.

Mauritanian authorities have indicated that it wishes to shift production from fish meal towards more value-added products and human consumption. They have introduced measures to limit the quantities of sardinella per meal plant to 10,000 tonnes, and several plants have established freezer facilities. The efficiency and practical application of this measure is uncertain, as there may be misreporting of supplies to fish meal plants. This line of thinking implies that EU can contribute on several aspects. Monitoring and control systems to ensure quotas are adhered to could benefit from EU contributions, both technically, financially and from know-how. EU firms have knowledge about preservation of

quality from catch through processing that could be beneficial. The EU-owned processor has indicated that there are technical barriers related to the vessels employed in the fishery that prevents more of catches being used for human consumption.

Better knowledge about the economic incentives facing the chain actors could support monitoring and control activities. This includes information about the economic profitability for the two primary processing alternatives fish meal and human consumption. If the current situation is based on short-sighted profit realization and race to fish conditions at sea, then achieving change in processing structure could be easier than if one has to work against the economic drivers. Monitoring and control would be crucial also in such a setting, as IUU fishing opportunities can lead to breakdown of economic incentives.

Changing the utilization of small pelagics may require considerable investment and human capital. Mauritania has not the best business environment, ranking low in the World Bank, having complicated tax regimes and corruption and opaqueness issues. This may hinder innovation and investment, and potentially slow a transition from fish meal to more value-added production. Increasing transparency in these and other areas will increase the likelihood of industry financing the economically most valuable production. Supporting the FiTi initiative in Mauritania could also be beneficial.

There are clear indications that EU companies are facing more restrictive standards than others. Thus, working towards more homogenous standards being applied for all participants operating within the fisheries industry can be beneficial for EU investments. This can perhaps be promoted through the SFPA negotiations and financial contributions.

5 The hake value chains and the fisheries in Mauritania, Senegal and in the Southwest Atlantic high seas

Main findings and lessons learned

Spain is the main market for hake and is supplied from several different hake fisheries around the world. Consumption is high in Spain, with hake being the most consumed species, but there are also extensive exports to other European countries such as Portugal and Italy. During the last decade, supplies from Argentine hake fished in the Southwest Atlantic has become increasingly important, and Spanish catches have increased from about 20 to 100,000 tonnes. The Argentine hake fishery by the Spanish fleet primarily takes place in the high seas. Catches are frozen on board, offloaded generally in Uruguay and transhipped to Spain for further processing and inclusion in the large hake value chain here. The Argentinean fleet is a major player in this fishery, taking his catches in their own EEZ. Other main hake fisheries hold MSC-certification, but as there is no RFMO managing the Southwest Atlantic, these fisheries are not certifiable due to lack of management, placing them at a potential disadvantage in the market. Other management arrangements might change this, if a bilateral agreement between Argentine and Spain is reached. The Hake stocks have been overexploited and are still fished at unsustainable levels, although there are signs of stock recovery. Thus, the supply of hake is likely to be reduced in the near future, if advice on the sustainable catch levels are followed by all fleets. This will influence especially the Spanish value chain through reduced supply, turnover and employment. The price effect is uncertain, as demand is generally decreasing, and frozen hake has substitutes in the market.

Spanish vessels also supply the market with hake from SFPA fisheries in Senegal and Mauritania. Catches in Senegal has shifted from fresh to predominantly frozen, and were about 3,000 tonnes in 2019. Mauritanian catches are both from fresh-fish and freezer trawlers. Catches are generally landed in Mauritania and Senegal where the fresh fish is frozen in processing plants and both categories are shipped to Spain for further processing and distribution. Thus, these fisheries contribute some to activity and employment in the host countries, in addition to the sailors employed, although labour intensity in these activities is relatively low. As this fish is exported, it does not contribute significantly to food supply in the host countries.

Potential policy recommendations

The SFPA and Southwest Atlantic high seas hake fisheries are part of mature and well-developed value chains. However, lack of management of the Argentine hake fishery is reducing the potential value of the product in European markets. An RFMO has not been possible due to the ongoing dispute between Argentine and the UK over the Malvinas/Falkland Islands sovereignty. The main recommendation for this fishery is to strive for achieving a management arrangement that include the most important players in the fisheries, to obtain a recognized sustainability certification that enable the product to

reach maximum value and compete evenly with other hake sources. There are other opportunities arising from innovations, market development and initiatives from firms that could provide value chain improvements. If markets for hake in the host countries or neighbouring countries develop and have sufficiently high willingness to pay, then landings could contribute more to local activity through increased processing and distribution. Ensuring harvesting at sustainable levels will be important to maintain current value adding and reduce the risk of reduced catches and activities. The local hake fisheries from the Senegalese artisanal fleet has expanded considerably in recent years. Continued expansion could come into conflict with allocations to EU vessels and could necessitate trade-offs to be made for Senegalese authorities in negotiations of future agreements.

In the Mauritanian SFPAs, other flagged fleets also target hake but are not subject to the same catch and activity reporting requirements as the EU vessels. This has resulted in uncertainties around actual catch levels and sustainability. The EU could promote equal reporting requirements to be applied for all fleets licensed in the fishery through SFPAs negotiations. A considerable amount of hake is also caught in the pelagic fisheries in Mauritania. EU could support measures to reduce such bycatch. This could be technological and fishing tactics development. Improving information and data sharing from onboard observers to operators has been identified as being potentially beneficial in this regard.

In Senegal, national hake fisheries are developing, in order to export to West Africa. Both in terms of supply and destination, EU is not affected. So, it is likely that EU would face end of the hake category in SFPAs soon or later. In this way, it is not relevant to define clear potential policy recommendation, since it is up to Senegal to decide.

6 Governance of the high Seas fisheries in the Southwest Atlantic

The fisheries on straddling and deep-water stocks in the Southwest Atlantic high seas are taking place outside any cooperative arrangement and there are no RFMOs governing the fisheries taking place. In the FarFish project we have analysed the barriers for establishing an RFMO or other international arrangement for governing the fisheries of the straddling fish stocks in this area, and identified some initiatives to overcome these barriers and improve the governance of the fisheries.

The main stocks are generally harvested beyond sustainable levels, the key commercial fisheries are taking place without any common international framework, irrespective of the fisheries or existing regulations of the coastal states, without regular exchange of information nor coordinated sharing of scientific or catch data. There is also a lack of implementation of already set international obligations such as resolutions and recommendations adopted by the UN General Assembly to take measures to map and protect vulnerable marine ecosystems in the area and minimise adverse impacts from bottom trawling in the high seas, where only one actor (EU/Spain) has acted and implemented a fishing closure for bottom trawling in nine areas.

Notwithstanding the lack of an RFMO for the Southwest Atlantic, there are and have been cooperative fisheries arrangements between the coastal states. There is a bilateral cooperation between Argentina and Uruguay through the Joint Technical Commission for the River Plate Maritime Front (CTMFM) established in 1973. The CTMFM adopts regulations for the Common Fisheries Zone of Argentina and Uruguay. In addition to cooperate on the assessment and management of shared stocks, it has organized and coordinated joint research surveys and other research activities. Of particular relevance for the high seas fisheries, it in 2011, 2014 and 2017 hosted international scientific symposiums on stock assessment and fisheries management. Another cooperative arrangement is the South Atlantic Fisheries Commission (SAFC) in the period 1990 – 2005. It was furthering cooperation between Argentina and the United Kingdom (UK) on behalf of the Falkland Islands /Malvinas, and SAFC brought together scientists and fisheries managers to discuss the implementation of measures to improve the conservation and management of commercially important fish stocks in the Southwest Atlantic, particularly those around the Falkland Islands /Malvinas. SAFC did not have decision making power nor adopted binding recommendations, but facilitated the exchange of fisheries data, joint research cruises, joint scientific analysis, and recommended coordinated conservation advice to the respective governments. The possibility, and need, to develop SAFC into a multilateral fisheries agreement, involving also DWFN was raised several times in SAFC, the first time in 1998, but without any real progress being made to its realisation. There have been talks between the governments of the UK and Argentina in 2016 and 2018 on the importance of data exchange on fish and squid stocks in the Southwest Atlantic and also on the need to re-establish the SAFC. So far however this has not been

realised, due to the longstanding dispute over the sovereignty over the Falkland Islands / Malvinas between Argentina and the UK.

The fishing activities taking place in the international waters in the Southwest Atlantic clearly needs to be governed through concerted, bi- or multilateral approaches. At the regional level, there is presently no institution or arrangement with governance capacity to “host” such cooperation, even though there is a possibility that CECAF could expand its scope of activities and thereby have the potential to evolve into an RFMO or advisory fisheries organisation in the future. Even the CTMFM could operate as a facilitator for scientific cooperation and data exchange. However, the sovereignty dispute over the Falklands Islands/Malvinas has so far hampered such solutions. Argentina has not been willing to date to enter into any multilateral arrangement that can imply a tacit recognition of the sovereignty of the UK as a coastal State in the ASW and acknowledge Malvinas/Falkland Island’s right to the fisheries resources and to establish an EEZ. Whilst the UK is unwilling to enter any arrangement as a DWFN.

In the absence of governmental cooperation, there are also initiatives at the non-governmental/ stakeholder level to promote the establishment of management arrangements to ensure the sustainable harvesting of the fisheries resources in the area. A current example is the Argentinian OPRAS (Organisation for the Protection of South Atlantic Fishery Resources), established in 2018, which in 2020 entered into a collaboration with the Spanish Association of Hake Fishing Freezer Vessel Owners (ANAMER) and Spanish Confederation of Fishing Organisations CEPESCA to that end.

The most important fisheries, the Argentine hake and Argentine shortfin squid, both straddling stocks and presumably overharvested, stand out as the first fisheries to address. The actors involved are identified, both the DWFNs and coastal states, but there are gaps in transparency and reporting of fishing activities particularly from non-EU vessels mainly targeting shortfin squid. A common approach should therefore ideally involve all the DWFNs, but initially at least the main DWFNs China, EU, Korea and Taiwan, as well as all the coastal states, including Argentina, UK (on behalf of the Falkland Islands/Malvinas), Uruguay and maybe Brazil. A pertinent question is however the willingness of all the key stakeholders involved in the fisheries, in particular the DWFNs to enter into any formal cooperative arrangement. The dispute between Argentina and the UK is also a significant barrier to the establishment of a common regulation, like establishing a RFMO or even a regional fisheries body. And neither China (as distant water flag state) nor Argentina (as coastal state) have ratified the UNFSA, which strengthened the obligation for states to cooperate to conserve and manage resources at the high seas. Still, China is member of the tuna RFMOs IOTC and ICCAT and to the Western and Central Pacific Fisheries Commission (WCPFC). Argentina on the other hand is only member of the Commission for the Conservation of Antarctic Marine Living Resources (CCAMLR). The lack of involvement of states with fishing fleets heavily involved in the fisheries in the Southwest Atlantic would pose a big challenge for the success of any cooperative arrangement or even eventually an RFMO.

The reasons for the lack of regional cooperation are first and foremost political. Still, the lack of commitment by all relevant states to enter into any kind of formal cooperation does not prevent the remaining actors from establishing cooperative arrangements. In the absence of a competent fisheries body and common regulations, a first step to improve the governance of the Southwest Atlantic high-seas fisheries could be to share scientific information and catch data at scientific symposiums. Such arrangements to a certain extent are already taking place at irregular events. A next step could be to initiate a more formal dialogue and eventually regular cooperation between research communities in the respective countries. Rather than bringing the issue to high political levels, research exchange handled at the level of scientific cooperation could function as a first and critical step to improve the fisheries governance of the straddling stocks in the southwest Atlantic. Such an approach allows stakeholders to show both entrepreneurial and intellectual leadership.

A type of leadership is the initiatives from the non-governmental and industry organisations. Rather than relying on concerted top-down processes and solutions, seeking bottom-up initiatives and solutions (like the joint cooperation between OPRAS-ANAMER-CEPESCA) creates new practices, and mentalities, for the governing the high seas fisheries in the South-West Atlantic that contribute in establishing the ground for improved governance.

The EU/Spanish implementation of the UNGA Resolution 61/105 through the closure of areas for bottom trawling in 2011 can also be considered an effort to show leadership in a politically tense environment. The potential for the EU to take a lead role in strengthening the governance and furthering cooperation between key actors are also improved with Brexit. When the UK is no longer an EU Member State, the EU can operate with a higher degree of credibility and trust independent of the sovereignty dispute between Argentina and the UK.

The way to make this fishery governable seems to be through a stepwise process, gradually involving more fisheries, more actors and expanding on the issues governed. Key actors, both state and non-state actors in fisheries governance (both sectoral and multistakeholder) can take on a leading role and contribute to gradually establish a regional system for cooperation and governance of the high seas fisheries of the Southwest Atlantic.

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